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Bond-slip laws for Natural Fibers in High Performance Cementitious Matrices

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ABSTRACT: The use of fibers as a dispersed reinforcement in cement-based materials is a common solution for enhancing post-cracking response of cementitious matrices in a class of materials generally referred to as Fiber-Reinforced Cementitious Composites (FRCCs). However, the use of natural fibers in FRCC is a relatively new trend, motivated by the lower cost of these fibers with respect to the “ordinary” industrial fibers, either made of steel or plastic materials. Although natural fibers present complex microstructure and wide heterogeneity, several researches have demonstrated their potential.

This paper presents is intended at identifying the bond-slip laws capable to describe the interaction of natural fibers with cementitious matrices. First, it summarizes the results of a wide series of pull-out tests carried out on sisal, curauá and jute fibers. Then, the experimental results are employed in an inverse identification procedure aimed at unveiling the key features of the aforementioned bond-slip laws. Finally, the obtained results in terms of relevant parameters, such as bond strength, ultimate slip and fracture energy in mode II of the fiber-matrix interface, pave the way for future studies intended at better understanding the structural response of FRCC with natural fibers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-Reinforced Cementitious Composites (FRCCs) are generally characterized by higher tensile and flexural strength, tougher and more ductile post-cracking behavior and superior durability performance (Banthia, 1994), as fibers promote a “bridging effect” across the opening cracks and lead to enhanced response in the post-peak branch of stress-strain relationships (Srivastava et al., 2013). This effect is controlled by several relevant parameters, such as fiber geometry, shape, dosage, orientation and distribution within the matrix, mechanical properties of fibers and bond interaction between fiber and cementitious matrix (Yoo et al., 2013).

Research activities have been recently developed for demonstrating the potential of using natural fibers, in lieu of the more common steel or plastic ones, in a class of materials often referred to as N-FRCC (Pacheco-Torgal and Jalali, 2011). Fibers obtained by processing leaves or stalks of different plants are currently under investigation (Toledo et al., 2003). For instance, sisal fibers are among the most promising: investigation about their morphology (in terms of transverse section area and shape) and mechanical properties have been recently developed: they demonstrate that the relevant geometric and physical parameters of these fibers are comparable to the ones of various types of industrial fibers (Silva et al, 2009).

This paper analyzes the bond behavior of sisal, curauá and jute fibers embedded in a cementitious matrix. More specifically, the results of several pull-out tests carried out on these natural fibers are firstly reported and, hence, the obtained force-slip curves are employed in inverse procedure intended at identifying the local bond-slip describing the interaction between fibers and matrices. Finally, some possible correlations between the main parameters of the aforementioned bond-slip laws and the fiber type and morphology are figured out.

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2 OUTLINE OF AN ANALYTICAL MODEL

An analytical model has been formulated for simulating the interaction between fiber and matrix in a pull-out process (Ferreira et al., 2016). It assumes that:

- the fiber behaves in a linear elastic way;
- the matrix is supposed to be perfectly stiff;
- the interaction between fiber and matrix is based on a bond-slip law τ - s , invariant throughout the fiber length.

As for the last point, the model assumes the following bilinear bond-slip law (Figure 1):

$$\tau(s) = \begin{cases} k_{el} \cdot s & \text{if } |s| \leq s_{el} \\ \tau_r - k_{in} \cdot (s - s_{el}) & \text{if } s_{el} < |s| \leq s_u \\ 0 & \text{if } |s| > s_u \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $k_{el} = \tau_{max}/s_{el}$ is the slip modulus of the elastic branch ending at a slip value s_{el} with a corresponding bond stress τ_{max} , τ_r is the residual bond stress, and k_{in} is the post-peak slip modulus (strictly positive), resulting in a linear variation of stresses from τ_r to τ_u , the latter being achieved for a slip s_u .

Figure 1. Bilinear bond-slip relationship.

The equilibrium equation of an infinitesimal element of fiber can be easily determined as already presented in several models already available in the literature (Caggiano et al., 2012), a general equilibrium condition can be determined (Figure 2):

$$\frac{d\sigma_f}{dz} - \frac{P_f}{A_f} \cdot \tau = 0 \quad (2)$$

Moreover, the axial strain ε_f developing in the fiber is strictly related to the interface slip s :

$$\varepsilon_f = \frac{ds}{dz} \quad (3)$$

Since the fiber is elastic $\sigma_f = E_f \varepsilon_f$ and, hence, equation (3) can be introduced in eq. (2), in order to obtain a well-known differential relationship between the second derivative of interface slips and the corresponding bond stress τ (Caggiano et al., 2012):

$$\frac{d^2 s}{dz^2} - \frac{P_f}{E_f A_f} \cdot \tau(s) = 0, \quad (4)$$

Figure 2. Local equilibrium conditions on a free infinitesimal element of fiber.

A step-wise analytical solution can be obtained by considering the various states of stresses of the fiber-to-matrix interface resulting from the bilinear bond-slip law represented in Figure 1. Further details on both the mathematical derivation and the numerical implementation of this solution are available in Ferreira et al (2016).

Based on the above assumptions, the full range analytical expression of the applied pull-out force F_0 can be, as a function of the displacement s_0 at the end of the fiber embedment, on the loaded side.

Moreover, F_0 also depends upon the actual bond-slip law assumed for describing the interface behavior. Hence, the following conceptual relationship can be written:

$$F_0 = F_0(s_0; \mathbf{q}), \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{q} is a vector that collects the five parameters describing the interface law described in Figure 1:

$$\mathbf{q} = [s_{el} \quad s_u \quad \tau_{max} \quad \tau_r \quad \tau_u]. \quad (6)$$

The aforementioned analytical model can be employed for determining the parameters describing the actual bond-slip interaction by means of an “inverse identification” procedure (Martinelli et al., 2012). More specifically, the following optimization problem has to be solved:

$$\bar{\mathbf{q}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{q}} \Delta(\mathbf{q}). \quad (7)$$

being

$$\Delta(\mathbf{q}) = \sum_{i=1}^n [F_0(s_{0,i}; \mathbf{q}) - F_{0,i}^{exp}]^2. \quad (8)$$

where $s_{0,i}$ is the displacement imposed on the free end of the fiber at the i -th increment of the experimental procedure, $F_{0,i}^{exp}$ is the corresponding force and n is the number of displacement increments either in the experimental process or the current numerical analysis.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Fibers

This study considered three types of fibers: sisal, curauá and jute. These fibers featured lengths ranging from 40 cm to 100 cm. All fibers underwent a preliminary washing treatment in hot water (80-100°C) intended at removing any existing residues, such as fats, waxes and mucilage, from their surface. Then, after drying, fibers were brushed by means of a laboratory metal comb with the aim to facilitate their cutting with a guillotine.

The sisal fibers were obtained from homonymous plants, whose scientific name is “*Agave sisalana*”: these plants are grown in farms located in the state of Bahia, Brazil. They were leaves in the form of long fiber bundles through the so-called “decortication” process, in which leaves are crushed by a rotating wheel with blunt knives.

The curauá fibers were supplied by Pematec, a dealer located in the city of Santarém, in the state of Pará, Brazil. They extracted from the leaves of “*Ananas erectifolius*”, present in Amazonia, by means of a process similar to the one adopted for sisal fibers.

Finally, the jute fibers also came from Amazonia. More specifically, they were extracted from the stem of the plant “*Corchorus capsularis*” by means of a process consisting of cutting, retting, shredding, drying, packing and classification.

3.2 Cement based matrix

The cementitious matrix of the N-FRCC investigated in this work was based on a binder consisting of 30% Portland cement CP-32 F II (NBR 11578, 1991), 30% metakaolin and 40% fly ash (in weight). As already demonstrated in previous researches (Silva et al., 2009), this amount of metakaolin guarantees durability of fibers within the cement matrix. Moreover, the presence of fly ash mainly aims at ensuring workability requirements: in fact, it induces a more uniform distribution of fibers within the cementitious matrix (Toledo Filho et al., 2009; Ferreira et al., 2014). The cementitious matrix was obtained by mixing two parts of binder for each part of sand, and adopting 0.4 as water-to-cement ratio.

The sand was processed in order to obtain a maximum diameter equal to 840µm. In addition, a superplasticizer (Glenium 51 - type PA) with solids content of 31% was used and, 0.8 kg/m³ of a viscosity modifier Rheomac UW 410 were also added with the aim to avoid segregation during the casting process. This matrix presented a flow table spread value of 450 mm, compressive strength at 7 and 28 days equal to 22 and 33.56 MPa, respectively. Moreover, static elastic modulus and tensile strength were equal to 13.27 GPa and 2.24 MPa, respectively.

3.3 Experimental procedures

Several tests were performed for characterizing natural fibers. First, the morphological characterization of fibers was carried out by means of a Hitachi TM3000 Scanning Electronic Microscope (SEM). More specifically, a sample was taken out of each fiber undergoing mechanical tests. The obtained images were, then, post-processed using *ImageJ*, a Java-based image processing program (<https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/>).

The mechanical performance of natural fibers was mainly investigated by performing tensile tests in a Shimadzu AG-X electromechanical testing machine, equipped with a load cell of 1.0 kN. The fibers, with a gage length of 40 mm, were glued to a paper mold

to get both a better alignment in the machine and a sufficient grip with the upper and lower jaws in accordance to ASTM (2014). For each type of fiber, 15 tests were performed at a displacement rate of 0.1 mm/min: the tensile strength of fibers was determined by dividing the maximum force measured in these tests by the transverse section area measured by analyzing the images obtained through SEM analyses.

Finally, to investigate the bond interaction between fibers and matrix, pull-out tests were carried out by means an electromechanical testing machine Shimadzu AG-X with a load cell of 1.0 kN: Figure 1 depicts the equipment employed in these pull-out tests, which were executed in displacement control at a rate of 0.1 mm/min. The test specimens were prepared in special molds and three different embedment lengths (namely, 5, 10 and 25 mm) were realized. The tests were performed after 6 days of curing in a fog room (100% RH) and a day of drying at $T=23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and relative humidity of $65\% \pm 3\%$.

Figure 3. Pullout test setup.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Morphological and mechanical characterization of natural fibers

Figure 4 depicts some outcomes of the microstructural analyses performed on the natural fibers.

Figure 4: Examples of cross sections: (a) Sisal, (b) Curauá and (c) Jute fibers.

It shows that, as expected, their transverse section is irregular in shape and non-uniform throughout the fiber length: Silva et al (2010) observed and categorized typical recurring shapes, such as horse-shoe-, arc- and twisted-shape sections.

Besides the qualitative classification of fibers morphology, a quantitative parameter, such as the Fiber Intrinsic Efficiency Ratio (FIER), was introduced for determining an objective measure of their shape (Naaman, 1999). It is defined as follows:

$$FIER_r = \frac{P_f}{P_{eq}} \quad (9)$$

where P_f is the actual fiber perimeter of the fiber and P_{eq} is the circumference of a cylindrical fiber characterized by the same cross sectional area A_f measured on the natural fiber. It is worth highlighting that the aforementioned perimeter and area are determined as average values throughout the fiber length; moreover. The values of FIER obtained for the sisal, curauá and jute fibers analyzed in this study present an average of 1.3 (ranging between 1.1 and 2.0), 3.4 (ranging between 1.7 and 7.9) and 4.3 (ranging between 2.5 and 6.2), respectively. This result confirms the natural fibers under investigation are characterized by a significantly irregular cross section, whose shape is far different from an ideally circular one. Moreover, the average values of FIER obtained for the three shapes observed by Silva et al (2010) turned out to be 1.21, 1.38 and 1.76, respectively. Moreover, the mechanical tests highlighted that the tensile strength of sisal, curauá and jute fibers is equal to 484, 632 and 250 MPa (with standard deviation 135, 138 and 89), respectively; moreover, the elastic moduli are equal to 19.5, 38.1 and 43.9 GPa (with standard deviation of 4.5, 18.0 and 12.3), respectively. These results indicate that the mechanical response of all kinds of fibers presents a relatively high scatter: this can be reasonably attributed to their intrinsically irregular morphology.

Finally, some examples of load-slip curves obtained in the tests mentioned in this section are plotted in Figure 5. More specifically, the results obtained from pull-out tests carried out on specimens of different bond length are represented therein. All specimens with 5 mm bond length exhibited a debonding failure. Particularly, the three types of fibers achieved an almost equal peak force with apparently different post-peak behavior: curauá exhibited the most ductile response, whereas a more abrupt decay in axial force was observed in jute fibers. Similar consideration can be drawn out in terms of failure mechanisms observed for 10-mm length specimens. However, in this case a more significant difference emerged in terms of stiffness of the elastic branch, whereas the response of curauá and jute turned out to be basically overlapped. Conversely, different responses were observed for the 25-mm specimens. Particularly, 25-mm jute fibers failed in tension and, hence, as a result of bond interaction, geometric properties and axial strength, the tests demonstrated that transfer length is, in fact, included between 10 and 25 mm.

5 INVERSE IDENTIFICATION OF THE BOND-SLIP LAWS

The phenomenological description, outlined at the end of the previous section, suggests some insights into the interaction between fibers and matrix. However, since the resulting force-slip laws are clearly influenced by several geometric parameters, such as FIER and bond length, a deeper interpretation of the material-level interaction between the various tested fibers and matrices should be achieved by taking duly into account the structural behavior of the system under consideration. More specifically, it can be as-

sumed that the fiber behaves like a rod-like element connected to a stiff matrix by means of a longitudinally invariant bond-slip law capable to describe the fracture process in mode II that leads to debonding. In other words, the experimental results can be interpreted in the light of the model outlined in Section 2 and, hence, the bond-slip law, generally depicted in Figure 1, can be identified through the inverse procedure mathematically described by eqs. (5)-(8).

Therefore, the inverse identification procedure was applied to all the force-slip curves obtained in experimental tests in which debonding failure was actually observed. Table 1 summarizes the average results obtained for the three types of fibers tested in the experimental program outlined in Section 3: the values determined for the five free components of vector \mathbf{q} described in eq. (6) are reported within the aforementioned table. Moreover, Table 1 also mentions the corresponding values of G_f , which can be easily determined from the five aforementioned parameters. For all these quantities, the corresponding coefficient of variation, determined on fifteen test results, is highlighted (as a percentage, in round brackets). Figure 6 shows the comparison between some of the experimental results and the corresponding numerical simulation carried out by assuming the values of Table 1 for identifying the actual bond-slip law.

Table 1. Parameters identifying the bond-slip laws for natural fibers.

Fiber	l_b [mm]	s_e [mm]	s_u [mm]	τ_{max} [MPa]	τ_r [MPa]	τ_u [MPa]	G_f [N/mm]
<i>Sisal</i>	5	0.18 (38)	3.06 (21)	0.39 (35)	0.29 (39)	0.20 (59)	0.77 (51)
	10	0.19 (40)	2.52 (32)	0.43 (44)	0.33 (39)	0.20 (49)	0.64 (56)
	25	0.14 (47)	2.52 (24)	0.24 (28)	0.11 (34)	0.04 (66)	0.20 (48)
<i>Curauá</i>	5	0.25 (55)	1.78 (46)	0.37 (65)	0.30 (75)	0.18 (71)	0.41 (94)
	10	0.29 (55)	3.10 (20)	0.35 (43)	0.17 (38)	0.11 (41)	0.45 (42)
	25	0.27 (72)	2.88 (23)	0.21 (49)	0.12 (38)	0.06 (82)	0.26 (38)
<i>Jute</i>	5	0.45 (40)	2.21 (34)	0.30 (15)	0.13 (38)	0.05 (76)	0.22 (53)
	10	0.46 (49)	2.63 (21)	0.34 (39)	0.21 (25)	0.04 (59)	0.33 (28)
	25	-	-	-	-	-	-

These results allows highlighting some considerations:

- Figure 6 demonstrates that the simplified law depicted in Figure 1 and the inverse identification procedure outlined in Section 2 are capable to achieve a significant accuracy in simulating the mechanical behavior and determining the relevant bond-slip laws, based on their global force-slip response observed on the tested specimens;
- the five parameters collected in the vector \mathbf{q} are often in the same order of magnitude, as derived from tests on 5 and 10 mm;
- conversely the values of both displacement and stress parameters in vector \mathbf{q} are generally lower when derived from the longest specimens: this is probably a result of the variability of the bond-slip law throughout the fiber, which is expected to be higher for longer fibers (and is actually neglected by the employed model);
- the values reported in Table 1 highlight that, for the same embedded length, the sisal fibers present the highest values in terms of G_f : this might be attributed to the intrinsic morphology of sisal fibers generally featuring higher surface roughness and more irregular cross section shape than the other natural fibers considered in this study.

Figure 5. Typical pull-out behavior of natural fibers

Figure 6. Experimental versus model

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper is intended as a contribution towards better understanding the interaction between natural fibers and cement-based matrices, which is the main feature controlling the mechanical behavior of natural fiber-reinforced cementitious composites (N-FRCC). First, the results of the geometric and mechanical characterization of three types of fibers, obtained from different plants, are outlined, along with the results of a series of pull-out tests intended at reproducing either tensile failure in the fiber or bond failure throughout the fiber-to-matrix interface. These results highlighted that the geometric and mechanical properties controlling the behavior of these fibers are somehow comparable to other kinds of “industrial” fibers already employed as spread reinforcement in FRCCs.

Second, an inverse identification procedure, based on a simplified bilinear bond-slip law (assumed invariant throughout the embedded length of the fiber), has been applied to the force-slip results obtained from pull-out tests in which no tensile rupture was observed: the procedure demonstrated its capability in identifying the bond interaction between fibers and matrix.

Third, the results obtained from the inverse identification procedure provide relevant insights into the potential of using natural fibers in FRCC. In fact, they highlight the superior performance of sisal fibers (i.e. in terms of resulting G_f), which emerge as the most suitable to be incorporated as spread reinforcement in cementitious composites. Furthermore, curauá fibers follow with their slightly lower value of G_f , whereas jute fibers exhibit a G_f in the order of two/three times lower than the sisal ones.

Finally, this study further confirms the experimental preliminary results recently published in the literature for demonstrating feasibility and potential of N-FRCC. Moreover, it provides readers with a structural engineer’s vision of their behavior, as it proposes a general identification procedure and reports reference values for the key mechanical parameters needed for predicting the structural response of members made of N-FRCC.

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